

Dvodnevno usposabljanje: Poletna šola EU managementa

Gradivo/Handout

Horizon Europe Training: Pillar 2

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Horizon Europe is the EU's key funding program for research and innovation with a budget of €95.5 billion. It aims to tackle climate change, help achieve the UN's Sustainable Development Goals, and boost the EU's competitiveness and growth. One of its main components is Pillar 2, which focuses on global challenges and European industrial competitiveness.

Pillar 2 of Horizon Europe is aimed at tackling major global challenges by supporting research and innovation across six clusters:

- **Health**
- **Culture, Creativity, and Inclusive Society**
- **Civil Security for Society**
- **Digital, Industry, and Space**
- **Climate, Energy, and Mobility**
- **Food, Bioeconomy, Natural Resources, Agriculture, and Environment**

These clusters are designed to foster systemic change and ensure that Europe remains a leader in scientific and technological advancements.

Emphasis on Excellence:

- **Scientific Excellence:**
 - Proposals must demonstrate a high degree of scientific quality and innovation. This involves presenting novel approaches, cutting-edge methodologies, and the potential to significantly advance the state of the art.
 - High-quality research should lead to breakthrough discoveries and advancements that address complex societal challenges.
- **Expertise and Experience:**
 - The track records of the researchers and institutions involved are crucial. Proposals should showcase their expertise and previous successes, underscoring their capability to achieve the project's ambitious goals.
 - Collaborations with leading institutions and researchers are encouraged to strengthen the proposal.
- **Interdisciplinary Approaches:**
 - Encourages collaborations across various disciplines to foster innovative solutions. Proposals should integrate knowledge and methods from different fields to address complex problems in a comprehensive manner.

Emphasis on Impact:

- **Societal and Economic Benefits:**
 - Proposals must clearly outline the potential societal and economic benefits of the research. This includes addressing significant societal challenges, improving quality of life, and contributing to economic growth.
 - Projects should create market opportunities and foster job creation, aligning with broader economic objectives.
- **Dissemination and Exploitation:**
 - Effective dissemination strategies are crucial for ensuring that research results reach relevant stakeholders and the broader public.
 - Proposals should include detailed plans for exploiting the research outcomes, ensuring that they are utilized in practical applications and have a lasting impact.
- **Policy Alignment:**
 - Projects should align with and support key EU policies, such as the European Green Deal, digital transformation strategies, and other relevant policy frameworks.
 - Aligning with policy priorities can enhance the relevance and impact of the research, ensuring it contributes to broader EU objectives.

Emphasis on Implementation:

- **Project Management and Coordination:**
 - Robust project management plans are essential. Proposals should include clear roles and responsibilities, detailed timelines, and effective risk management strategies.
 - Efficient coordination among partners is vital for successful project execution.
- **Resource Allocation:**
 - Proper allocation and management of resources, including budget, personnel, and infrastructure, are crucial. Proposals should ensure that resources are used effectively to achieve project objectives.
 - Transparent and efficient use of resources can enhance the project's credibility and feasibility.
- **Sustainability:**
 - Long-term sustainability plans should be included, detailing how the project outcomes will be sustained beyond the funding period.
 - Proposals should explore potential for future funding, partnerships, and other means to continue the project's impact.